

Capital Structure Performance of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited: By Testing Trade-off and Pecking Order Theories

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ABSTRACT

Capital structure is key discipline of financial operations of steel industry. This researcher constitutes an attempt to identify the impact of Capital Structure Performance of two leading and rank one public and private sector steel companies. The analysis was done with the Capital Structure and its importance on financial performance of select two steel producing companies during year 2014-15 to 2018-19 (Five years) of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited. The idea of this paper is to examine the extent to which growth determines of Capital Structure performance of these two companies by testing of Trade-off and Pecking Order Theories. This is done by examining the Capital Structure components consisting of long-term debt with Capital Structure determinants of SAIL and TSL and then testing the resulting ideas empirically. This paper may provide useful insights for the interested stakeholders, such as customers, depositors, borrowers and investors etc.

Keywords: Capital Structure, Long term debt, stakeholders, Trade-off Theory, Pecking Order Theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

Capital structure refers to the mix of long-term sources of funds such as debentures, long term debt, preference shares capital and equity share capital including Reserves and surpluses (i.e. retained earnings). Every time the firm makes an investment decision, it also makes financial decision at the same time. The investment projects of a company can be financed either by increasing the owners claims or the creditors' claims. The owners' claims increase when the firm raises funds by issuing common shares or by retaining the earning; the creditor's claims increase by borrowings.

The financing or capital structure decision is a significant managerial decision. It influences the shareholders return and risk. Consequently, the market value of the share may be affected by the capital structure decision. The company will have to plan its capital structure initially at the time of its promotion. The decision will involve a Statement of the existing capital structure and factors which will govern the decision like present shareholders equity position strengthen by retention of earnings. Thus, the dividend decision also has a bearing on the capital structure decision of the company.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL OF THE DETERMINANTS OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE

The present paper attempts to explain the determination of variables in the capital structure of Steel Authority of India (SAIL) and Tata Steel Company (TSL). Due to global competition steel companies are now giving more emphasis on research and development activities and use advanced technology. This has important implications for managerial decision making. This study has tried to understand the role of knowledge capital and determinant factors in capital structure decision of SAIL and TSL. The following are the theoretical standpoints, a number of empirical studies have identified firm-level characteristics that affect the capital structure of companies. For examining the various factors that affect the capital structure of the SAIL and TSL, the present study considers testing of Trade-off and Pecking Order Theories and the following nine factors have been taken as independent variables in the present study. These factors are sales size, growth, profitability, interest coverage ratio, tangibility, NDT, assets size, income variability and liquidity.

3. AIM OF THE RESEARCH

The aim of this research is to determine the approach adopted by SAIL and TSL operating in steel sector while establishing their capital structure, and to set significant level of factors and applicable modern capital structure theories, which they consider while using external sources.

4. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Main objectives of the Paper is as follows

- ❖ To study and analyze the capital structure determinants of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.
- ❖ To review the importance of trade-off theory and pecking theory.
- ❖ To examine the applicability of Trade-off and Pecking order theories for the Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:

H₁: There is no a positive and significant relationship between Long Term Debt Leverage and Capital Structure determinants.

H₂: There is no impact of Trade-off theory and Pecking order theory on capital structure leverages.

6. METHODOLOGY

The design of the present study is descriptive and analytical in nature to covers the period of five years from 2015 to 2019. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfill our objectives that have been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data was collected from the officials and other employees through interviews and discussions regarding different aspects of the SAIL and TSL.

The study is also based on the secondary data obtained from the audited balance sheets and profit & loss accounts, operational reports, budgets, manuals and also the annual reports of SAIL and TSL. Besides, the facts, figures and findings advanced in similar earlier studies and the Annual and Financial Reports and Government publications are also used to supplement the secondary data.

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as descriptive, correlation, Regression and t-test are used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS soft ware.

7. CAPITAL STRUCTURE KEY COMPONENTS

Dependent variable

Long Term Debt Leverage: This leverage characterization utilizes just for the Long-term debts over the total assets. Titman and Wessels (1988) and others used long-term debt in their determinants study.

$$\text{Leverage (LTD)} = \frac{\text{Long Term Debt}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

Independent variables

The independent variables like size of sales, growth, profitability, interest coverage ratio, income variability, size of total assets, non-debt tax shield, income tax, business risk and size of employees are used as the determinants to analyze the dependent variable i.e., the debt ownership structure. Multiple Regression analysis is used to identify the various factors that influence debt financing pattern. Supplementing this analysis, correlation analysis has been used for a one-to-one relationship between the variables.

(a) **Size:** Firm size may be positively or negatively related to leverage. Large firms may exercise economies of scale, have bitterly manages. Large size may enable greater specialization. It may also measure a firm's market power or the level of concentration in the industry.

$$\text{Size} = \text{Log} (\text{Sales})$$

(b) Growth: The theoretical view of the relationship between growth and leverage is undetermined. In line with the agency theory of debt, conflicts between owners and lenders point to a negative correlation between growth opportunities and leverage due to two problems.

Where

$$\text{Growth} = \frac{\text{Assets (T)} - \text{Assets (T-1)}}{\text{Assets (T-1)}}$$

Assets (T) = Assets in current year
Assets (T-1) = Assets in previous year

(c) Tangibility: (TANG) is the characteristic that an asset can be used as collateral to secure debt. According to trade-off hypothesis, tangible assets acts as collateral and provide security to lenders in the event of financial distress. The ratio of fixed assets to total assets represents the degree of assets' tangibility.

$$\text{Tangibility} = \frac{\text{Net Fixed Assets}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

(d) Profitability: It is one of the capital structure determinant. It measures relationship between profitability and leverage.

Profitability = $\frac{\text{PBIT}}{\text{Total Assets}}$
Where
PBIT = Profit before Interest and Tax

(e) Interest Coverage Ratio: It is the determinant to explain firm ability to pay its fixed payments after expenses. Higher the ratio is greater the capacity of the firm to serve debt, which consequently results into large deployment of the debt. Further, trade-off theory implies that ICR and leverage are negatively correlated, but pecking order theory suggests positive relation.

$$\text{Interest Coverage Ratio} = \frac{\text{PBIT}}{\text{Interest}}$$

Where
PBIT= Profit before Interest and Tax

(f) Non-debt tax shields:

Tax: Effective tax rate calculated as income tax paid to earnings before tax. This variable is used as a proxy for tax benefit, which appears with higher levels. It has been taken depreciation to total assets as a proxy.

(g) Assets Size: The firm's assets size is one of the common variables used in explain a company's level of debt. There is considerable evidence that the assets size of a firm plays an important role in the capital structure decision. A positive relationship is expected between firm size and its leverage. Size of the firm is measured by natural logarithm. For this study, natural logarithm of the assets is used as a proxy for the firm's size.

(h) Income Variability: It can be observed that Income variability is a measure of business risk. Since higher variability in earnings indicates that the probability of bankruptcy increases, we can expect that firms with higher income variability have lower leverage.

$$\text{Income Variability} = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation of EBIT}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

(i) Liquidity: According to the packing order theory, firms with high liquidity are not likely to have high debt ratios as they have sufficient cash with them. So as per this theory, there is a negative relationship between debt and liquidity.

8. ANALYSIS OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE DEPENDENT VARIABLES (LEVERAGES)

In this paper, capital structure has been treated as a dependent variable. It has been measured in two forms by taking into leverage ratio.

Long Term Debt Leverage: This leverage characterization utilizes just the Long-term debts over the total assets.

An attempt is made to examine the above two leverage variables with capital structure of SAIL and TSL are presented in table 1 from the year 2014-15 to 2018-19.

Table-1, Statement of Long-term Debt Leverage

Year	SAIL			TSL		
	Long-term Debt	Total Assets	Leverage	Long-term Debt	Total Assets	Leverage
2014-15	34842	78347	0.44	34478	1,01,142	0.34
2015-16	39943	79139	0.50	36776	85688	0.43
2016-17	46514	82523	0.56	36229	85,888	0.42
2017-18	50706	86420	0.59	33015	96,805	0.34
2018-19	51056	89208	0.57	34418	1,07,148	0.32
Mean	44,612	83,127	0.53	34,938	95,334	0.37
S. D	7,063	4,662	0.06	1,517	9,457	.051

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

The debt ratios (Leverages) explain about the debt portion in the total assets of both the firms SAIL and TSL. It is seen from the above table that SAIL has a more portion of the total debt and long-term debt on its total assets. Since the firm is maintaining the excess of funds as debt. Actually, debt funds have more risk when compared to equity funds.

Long term debt leverage for SAIL was at the highest level in the year 2017-18, i.e. 0.59 and lowest level was seen in the year 2014-15, i.e. 0.44 and average leverage was 0.53 times.

On the other hand, TSL capital structure leverage it is found from the above table. It is seen maximum of long-term debt leverage i.e. 0.43 times in the year 2015-16 and minimum leverage was 0.32 times in the year 2018-19. TSL average debt leverages for the past five years total debt leverage is 0.37. Comparatively, low financial risk is observed on TSL.

9. ANALYSIS OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

(i) Size (Sales)

We try to examine and understand the sales variable; it is one of the capital structure determinant variables for SAIL and TSL. It measures market power and level of concentration in the above company

Size = Log (Sales)

Table: 2 Statement of Size (Sales)

Year	SAIL		TSL	
	Sales	Log of Sales	Sales	Log of Sales
2014-15	51,149	4.71	46,577	4.67
2015-16	43,875	4.64	42,697	4.63
2016-17	49,767	4.69	53,261	4.72
2017-18	58,962	4.77	60,519	4.78
2018-19	66,967	4.82	70,611	4.85

Mean	54,144	4.73	54,733	4.73
S. D	8,961	0.07	11,171	0.08

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

It is observed from the table 2, sales size variable of the SAIL and TSL for the past five years. SAIL has maximum sales size, which is resulted in the year 2018-19 i.e. log 4.82; it is found that maximum sales occurred in that year. Minimum sales size was log 4.64 in the year 2015-16 and average sales size for the past five years was log 473.

On the other hand, TSL, maximum and minimum sales size is observed in the year 2010-11 and 2001-02 i.e. log 854. and log 4.63 respectively. An average sale was log 4.73. Low spread is observed in favor of SAIL. Here, it is observed that sales trend is equal to the both the firms.

(ii) Growth

$$\text{Growth} = \frac{\text{Assets (T)} - \text{Assets (T-1)}}{\text{Assets (T-1)}}$$

Table: 5.3 Statement of Growth

Year	SAIL			TSL		
	Assets(T)	Assets(T-1)	Growth %	Assets(T)	Assets(T-1)	Growth %
2014-15	63,432	-	-	40,585	-	-
2015-16	75,352	11,920	18.79	52,846	12,261	31.21
2016-17	81,886	6,534	8.67	78,281	25,435	48.45
2017-18	92,454	10,568	12.9	80,955	2,674	3.42
2018-19	98,302	5,848	6.32	84,163	3,208	3.96
Mean	82,285	6975	9.32	67,366	28,944	17.48
S. D	13,817	4675	20,825	19,455	41,399	2134

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

From the Table No. 3, It is observed that the growth (sales) variable of the SAIL and TSL for the past five years. SAIL has decreasing sales trend to all the year, except in year 2014- 15 and 2018-19. Highest level and lowest level growth resulted in the year 2015-16 and 2018-19 are 18.79 times and 6.32 times respectively. On the other hand, TSL, maximum recorded 48.45 times in the year 2016-17 and minimum recorded 3.96 times in the year 2017-18. Computed average growth rate is 9.32 and 17.48 times respectively.

It is observed that growth rate of TSL is better than SAIL.

(iii) Profitability

$$\text{Profitability} = \frac{\text{PBIT}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

Table: 4 Statement of Profitability

Year	SAIL			TSL		
	PBIT	Total Assets	Profitability (%)	PBIT	Total Assets	Profitability (%)

2014-15	5586	78347	7.13	12,482	1,01,142	12.34
2015-16	-2,305	79139	-2.91	6,354	85688	7.41
2016-17	357	82523	0.43	11,587	85,888	13.52
2017-18	5,129	86420	5.93	13,176	96,805	13.61
2018-19	9,877	89208	11.07	22,854	1,07,148	21.33
Mean	3,729	83,127	4.33	13,291	95,334	13.64
S. D	4,769	4,662	5.55	52,9	9,457	4.99

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

From the Table No.4, It is found that the profitability variable of the SAIL and TSL. The minimum and maximum profitability of are seen (2.91) percent and 11.07 percent during the year 2014-15 and 2018-19 of SAIL and average Profitability was 4.33 percent for the past five years. On comparison, TSL, maximum and minimum profitability are recorded 7.41 percent and 21.33 percent in the year 2015-16 and 2018-18 and average Profitability was 13.64 percent. Overall the result of profitability, TSL is better than SAIL for all five years from 2015 to 2019.

v) Interest Coverage Ratio

$$\text{Interest Coverage Ratio} = \text{PBIT} / \text{Interest}$$

Table: 5 Statement of Interest Coverage (ICR)

Year	SAIL			TSL		
	PBIT	Interest	ICR(Times)	PBIT	Interest	ICR(Times)
2014-15	5586	1,454	3.84	12,482	1,976	5.32
2015-16	-2,305	2,300	-1.00	6,354	1,848	3.44
2016-17	357	2,528	0.14	11,587	2,689	4.31
2017-18	5,129	2,823	1.82	13,176	2,811	4.69
2018-19	9,877	3,155	3.13	22,854	2,824	8.09
Mean	3,729	2,452	1.59	13,291	2,530	3.55
S.D	4,769	643.57	2.01	52,98	477.57	1.77

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

It is observed from Table- 5, Interest Coverage Ratio variable of the SAIL and TSL for the past five years. SAIL has fluctuated trend for ICR to all the years. Highest level and lowest level ICR were seen in the year 2015-16 and 2016-17 were 3.84 times and (1) times respectively. On comparison, TSL has increasing trend highest level and lowest level this ratio is observed 8.09 times and 3.44 times during the year 2016-17 and 2018-19 respectively. But higher average interest coverage ratio was seen in favor of SAIL than the TSL (i.e.1.59 times and 3.55 times). Here, it is identified that the higher interest charges were paid by TSL than SAIL for the past five years.

(v) Tangibility

$$\text{Tangibility} = \text{Net Fixed Assets/Total Assets}$$

Table: 6 Statement of Tangibility

Year	SAIL			TSL		
	Net Fixed Assets	Total Assets	Tangibility (%)	Net Fixed Assets	Total Assets	Tangibility (%)
2014-15	63,432	78347	82.24	40,585	1,01,142	40.13
2015-16	75,352	79139	95.21	52,846	85688	61.67
2016-17	81,886	82523	99.22	78,281	85,888	91.14
2017-18	92,454	86420	106.98	80,955	96,805	83.63
2018-19	98,302	89208	110.19	84,163	1,07,148	78.55
Mean	82,285	83,127	98.77	67,366	95,334	71.02
S.D	13,817	4,662	10.99	19,455	9,457	20.38

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL.

From the Table No-6, it is found that Tangibility of the SAIL and TSL for the past five years. Minimum and maximum tangibility can be seen i.e. 8.24 percent and 110.19 percent in the 2015-16 and 2018-19 of SAIL and got 98.77 percent average tangibility for the past five years. On the other hand, TSL, maximum and minimum tangibility was recorded 78.55 percent and 40.13 percent in the year 2018-19 and 2015-16. Average rate of tangibility was 71.02 percent. Higher Tangibility is seen in favor of SAIL than TSL. As the result of tangibility, it is found that SAIL has been maintaining more fixed assets to total assets ratio than the TSL.

(vi) Non-Debt Tax Shield

$$\text{Non-Debt Tax Shield} = \text{Depreciation} / \text{Total Assets}$$

Table: 7: Statement of Non-Debt Tax Shield (NDT)

Year	SAIL			TSL		
	Depreciation	Total Assets	NDT (%)	Depreciation	Total Assets	NDT (%)
2014-15	1,773	78347	2.26	1,998	1,01,142	1.97
2015-16	2,402	79139	3.03	2,962	85688	3.46
2016-17	2,680	82523	3.25	3,542	85,888	4.12
2017-18	3,065	86420	3.55	3,727	96,805	3.85
2018-19	3,385	89208	3.92	3,803	1,07,148	3.55
Mean	2,661	83,127	3.20	3,206	95,344	3.39
S. D	621	4662	0.62	752	9457	0.8

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

It is seen from Table -7, Non-Debt Tax Shield variable of the SAIL and TSL for the past five years. Highest and lowest level of NDT was seen i.e. .932 percent and 2.26 percent in the year 2018-19 and 2015-16 of SAIL got an average NDT 3.20 percent during the study period. On comparison, it is observed highest and lowest level of Non-Debt Tax Shield was

observed 4.12 percent and 1.97 percent during 2016-17 and 2014-15 respectively. An average NDT for the past five years was 3.39 percent.

Higher Non tax shield is seen in favour of TSL than SAIL. As seen overall results of NDT, it is observed Depreciation to total assets ratio for the both the companies has been fluctuating trend. Comparatively, it is found that higher depreciation charges are borne by TSL than SAIL.

(vii) Size (Total Assets)

$$\text{Size} = \text{Log (Total Assets)}$$

Table: 8 Statement of Total Assets Size

Year	SAIL		TSL	
	Total Assets	Log of Total Assets	Total Assets	Log of Total Assets
2014-15	78347	4.89	1,01,142	5.00
2015-16	79139	4.90	85688	4.92
2016-17	82523	4.92	85,888	4.93
2017-18	86420	4.94	96,805	4.99
2018-19	89208	4.95	1,07,148	5.03
Mean	83127	4.9	53349	4.97
S.D	4662	0.025	9457	0.048

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and

It can be seen from Table -8, shows Total Assets Size variable of the SAIL and TSL for the past five years. SAIL has maximum assets size resulted in the year 2018-19 i.e. log 4.95. Hence, it is evident that more assets are maintained that year. Minimum assets size was log 4.89 in the year 2014-15 and average sales size was log 4.9. On the other hand, TSL, maximum and minimum assets size was seen in the year 2018-19 and 2015-16 respectively i.e. log 5.03 and log 4.92 and an average sale was log 97. Finally, it is observed that assets growth rate of TSL is better as compared to SAIL.

Income variability = Standard Deviation of PBIT to Total Assets

Table: 5.9 Statement of Income Variability

Year	SAIL				TSL			
	PBIT	S.D of PBIT	Total Assets	Income variability (%)	PBIT	S.D of PBIT	Total Assets	Income variability (%)
2014-15	5586	4769	78347	6.09	12,482	5982	1,01,142	5.91
2015-16	-2,305	4769	79139	6.03	6,354	5982	85688	6.98
2016-17	357	4769	82523	5.78	11,587	5982	85,888	6.96
2017-18	5,129	4769	86420	5.52	13,176	5982	96,805	6.18
2018-19	9,877	4769	89208	5.35	22,854	5982	1,07,148	5.58
Mean	3729	4769	83127	5.75	13291	5982	95334	6.322

S.D	4769	0.000	4662	0.32	5982	0.000	9457	0.63
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Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

(viii) Income variability

From the Table No. 9, it is found that Income variability of SAIL and TSL for the past five years. Minimum and maximum of income variability were 6.09 percent and 5.35 percent seen in the year 2015-16 and 2018-19 of SAIL and got 5.75 percent average income variable for the past five years. On comparison with Tata Steel Limited, its minimum and maximum income variable has been recorded 5.58 percent and 6.98 percent in the year 2015-16 and 2017-18 respectively. Average income variable was 6.32 percent. Higher income variability is seen in favors of TSL than SAIL.

(ix) Liquidity

Liquidity = Cash and Cash equivalent/Current Liabilities

Table: 10 Statement of Liquidity

Year	SAIL			TSL		
	Cash and Cash Equivalent	Current Liabilities	Liquidity Ratio (%)	Cash and Cash Equivalent	Current Liabilities	Liquidity Ratio (%)
2014-15	35,390	20,472	1.73	16,089	14,721	1.09
2015-16	34,567	24,694	1.39	20,193	23,571	0.86
2016-17	39,302	28,587	1.37	25,783	31,125	0.83
2017-18	45,047	34,570	1.30	30,659	34,344	0.89
2018-19	47,956	35,150	1.36	27,312	35,453	0.77
Mean	40452	28694	1.43	24007	27842	0.89
S.D	5895	63321	0.71	5822	8680	0.12

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

From the Table No.10, it is found that Liquidity of the SAIL and TSL for the past five years. Minimum and maximum liquidity was seen i.e.1.3 times and 1.73 times in the 2018-19 and 2014-15 respectively for SAIL. It got 1.43 times average liquidity for the past five years. On the other hand, TSL, maximum and minimum liquidity was recorded 1.9 times and 0.77 times in the year 2014-15 and 2018-19. Average rate of liquidity was 0.89 times. Higher liquidity is seen in favour of SAIL than TSL. As the result of liquidity, it is found that SAIL has been maintaining more Cash and Cash equivalent to Current Liabilities ratio.

Table: 11 Statement of Employees Size

Year	SAIL		TSL	
	No. Employees	Log of No. Employees	No. Employees	Log of No. Employees
2014-15	93,352	4.97	36,957	4.57

2015-16	88,655	4.95	35,439	4.55
2016-17	82,934	4.92	34,989	4.54
2017-18	76,870	4.85	34,072	4.53
2018-19	72,339	4.86	32,984	4.52
Mean	82830	4.91	34888	4.54
S.D	8518	0.05	1490	0.02

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL

It is observed from the table 11, employees size variable of the SAIL and TSL for the past five years. SAIL has maximum and minimum employee size, which are resulted in the year 2015-16 i.e. log 4.97 and log 4.91 in the year 2018-19 and average sales size for the past five years was log 4.91.

On the other hand, TSL, maximum and minimum employee size is observed in the year 2010-11 and 2001-02 i.e. log 4.57. and log 4.52 respectively. An average sale was log 4.54. Low spread is observed in favor of SAIL. Here, it is observed that employee trend decreasing and is equal to the both the firms.

10. CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Correlation is concern describing the strength of relationship between two variables. In this study, the correlation co-efficient analysis is undertaken to find out the relationship between capital structure leverages and capital structure determinants of both SAIL and TSL. The measure of correlation is called the co-efficient of correlation. It is denoted by 'r'. This correlation results showed in Table No. 12.

Table: 12 Statement of Correlation between Long term Debt and Capital Structure Determinants

Variable	SAIL			TSL		
	Correlation	p-value	Remarks	Correlation	p-value	Remarks
Sales (Size)	0.54	.342	Insignificant	-0.68*	.203	Significant
Growth	-0.70	.302	Insignificant	0.91	.090	Insignificant
Tangibility	0.95*	.015	Significant	0.15	.812	Insignificant
Profitability	0.16	.801	Insignificant	-0.71	.178	Insignificant
ICR	-0.19	.765	Insignificant	-0.78	.116	Insignificant
Total Assets (Size)	0.91*	.032.	Significant	-0.99*	.002	Significant
Income Variability	-0.87*	.050	Significant	0.97*	.005	Significant
Non-Tax Debt	0.92*	.027	Significant	0.36	.551	Insignificant
Liquidity	-0.91*	.032	Significant	-0.19	.755	Insignificant
Employee (Size)	-0.90*	.033	Significant	0.26	.679	Insignificant

* Significant at 5% level, the result is not significant at $p < 0.05$.

Source: Computed

Table 12 reveals that the Correlation between Long-term Debt Leverage and Capital Structure Determinants for SAIL and TSL. It can be seen that assets size, profitability, tangibility, non-debt tax and total assets size are the determinants have positive and remain determinants showed negative relationship with long-term debt variable of SAIL. On the other hand, TSL, growth, tangibility, non-debt tax, income variability and employee size showed positive and remain determinants showed negative relationship with long-term debt leverages.

As per the p-values, it can be seen tangibility, income variability, non-tax debt, liquidity and employee size have significant and other variables are insignificant statistically at 5% level of SAIL. On other hand TSL, sales size, total assets and income variability are significant and other variables insignificant at 5 % level.

11. REGRESSION ANALYSIS

An attempt is made to examine and test the explanatory power of the conventional theoretical framework of firm specific determinants of capital structure. We try to apply Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regressions are run on firm level data, with leverage (Long term Debt) as the dependent variable and the firm specific factors as the independent variables. Regression analysis is undertaken to find out the relationship between capital structure leverages and capital structure determinants of both SAIL and TSL. Long-term Debt Regression Coefficients are shows in Table No.-13

Table: 13 Long term Debt Regression Coefficients relating to Capital Structure determinants of SAIL and TSL

	SAIL		TSL	
	Un Standardized B	Standardized Beta	Un Standardized B	Standardized Beta
Constant (LD)	-12.04	-	Constant (LD)	-2.245
Sale Size	-.004	-.314	Sale Size	.036
Growth	.000	-.025	Growth	-.061
Profitability	-.788	-.818	Profitability	.639
ICR	-.458	-.285	ICR	-.213
Tangibility	.002	.251	Tangibility	-.036
NDT	.003	.015	NDT	.730
Total Assets	.025	0.776	Total Assets	.018
Income variable	.069	2.527	Income variable	.007
Liquidity	0.076	.451	Liquidity	.653
Employee Size	3.439	3.865	Employee Size	.774

Source: Computed.

It can be observed from Table-13 indicates Regression unstandardized and standardized coefficients of capital structure (Long-term Debt) and its determinant factors. It can be seen that the tangibility, income variability, liquidity, assets size and ICR are the determinants have positive relationship, whereas sales size, growth and profitability, employee size are showed negative relationship with total debt variable (dependent variable) of SAIL. The regression analysis also supports the correlation analysis, indicating that these capital structure determinants have explained the capital structure leverage. Further, we can see all results are statistically significant (p=nil) at level of 0.05.

On the other hand, TSL, it can be seen that the coefficient determinants of capital structure i.e. sales size, profitability, liquidity and NDT, employee size are showed positive and remained variables showed negative relationship with long-term debt leverage. The regression analysis also supports the correlation analysis, indicating that these capital structure determinants have explained the capital structure leverage. Further, we can see all results are statistically significant (p=nil) at level of 0.05.

Hence the capital structure extracted for these statistical analyses can be summarized as follows:

SAIL:

Regression Model (LD) = -12.044 - 0.004SalesSize + 0.000Growth - 0.788Profitability - 0.458ICR + 0.002Tangibility + NDT + 0.025TotalAssets + 0.069IncomeVariability + .076Liquidity + 3.439Employee Size.

TSL:

Regression Model (LD) = -2.245 - 0.036SalesSize - 0.061Growth + 0.639Profitability - 0.213ICR + 0.036Tangibility + 0.730NDT + 0.018TotalAssets + 0.007IncomeVariability + .0653Liquidity + .774Employee Size.

Testing of Hypothesis (Capital structure and Its Determinant Variables)

In this section, two hypotheses each hypothesis includes ten sub-hypotheses are tested using correlation coefficient to know the relationship strength and t- test used hypothesis for result. The simplest formula for computing the appropriate **t value** to test significance of a correlation coefficient employs the t distribution:

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$$

The **degrees of freedom** for entering the t-distribution is $N - 2$. Table value of (5-2) i.e. 3 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 3.182 for two tailed test. The hypotheses are re-stated as follows:

Test of Significance (Using capital structure Determinants)

Hypothesis 1 (H₀): H₁. There is no a positive and significant relationship between Long Term Debt Leverage and Capital Structure determinants.

Table: 14 Total debt and Capital Structure determinants Sub-Hypotheses

Specific Factors	Magnitude and Direction of Hypothesis
Hypothesis S1	Assets size has no positive effect on leverage
Hypothesis S2	Growth has no positive effect on leverage
Hypothesis S3	Profitability has no positive effect on leverage
Hypothesis S4	Interest coverage ratio has no positive effect on leverage
Hypothesis S5	Tangibility has no positive effect on leverage
Hypothesis S6	Non-Debt Tax has no positive effect on leverage
Hypothesis S7	Total Assets Size has no positive effect on leverage
Hypothesis S8	Income Variability has no positive effect on leverage.
Hypothesis S9	Liquidity has no positive effect on leverage
Hypothesis S10	Employee Size has no positive effect on leverage

Source: predictions.

Table: 15, Correlation and t-test results for Long-Term Debt Leverage and Capital Structure Determinants

Determinants	SAIL				TSL			
	'r' value	Correlation result	't' value	Hypothesis result	'r' value	Correlation result	't' value	Hypothesis result
Sale Size	0.54	Positive	//1.11//	Accepted	-0.68	High Negative	//1.61//	Accepted
Growth	-0.70	High Negative	//1.70//	Accepted	0.91	High Positive	//3.82//	Rejected
Profitability	0.95	High Positive	//5.20//	Rejected	0.15	Positive	//0.26//	Accepted
ICR	0.16	Positive	//0.28//	Accepted	-0.71	High Negative	//1.74//	Accepted
Tangibility	-0.19	Negative	//0.33//	Accepted	-0.78	High Negative	//2.16//	Accepted
NDT	0.91	High Positive	//3.82//	Rejected	-0.99	High Negative	//12.12//	Rejected
Total Assets	-0.87	High Negative	//3.07//	Accepted	0.97	High Positive	//6.86//	Rejected
Income variable	0.92	High Positive	//4.11//	Rejected	0.36	Positive	//0.67//	Accepted
Liquidity	-0.91	High Negative	//3.82//	Rejected	-0.19	Negative	//0.33//	Accepted
Employee Size	-0.90	High Negative	//3.58//	Rejected	0.26	Positive	//0.47//	Accepted

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed),

Source: Computed.

Table 15 reveals that the Correlation between Long Term Debt Leverage and Capital Structure Determinants for SAIL and TSL. It can be seen that profitability, NDT, income variability, liquidity and employee size are the determinants have positive whereas remain determinants showed negative relationship with long-term debt variable of SAIL. On the other hand, TSL, growth, NDT and total assets showed positive and remain determinants showed negative relationship with total debt leverages.

As per the t-test results, it is clear that the computed values of above stated sub-hypotheses are lies below the critical value of 't' at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted for both SAIL and TSL. Hence, the relation can be strong and no significant difference between long-term debt leverage and capital structure determinants. This is justified that correlations exist between the total debt leverage and capital structure determinants.

Testing for the applicability of the Trade-off Theory and Pecking order Theory

In present paper, an attempt is made to examine the applicability of these two theories for the Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited to identify the relationship between explanatory variables of capital structure and leverage.

Table: 16 Relationship between Explanatory Variables and Leverage (SAIL) with Trade-off and Pecking order Theories.

Variables	Expected Relationship		Actual Relationship and β Coefficients	
	Trade-off Theory	Pecking Order Theory	Actual Relationship	Long term Debt
Sale Size	Positive	Negative	Negative	-.004
Growth	Negative	Positive	Positive	.000
Profitability	Positive	Negative	Negative	-.788
ICR	Negative	Positive	Negative	-.458
Tangibility	Positive	No relationship is specified	Positive	.002
NDT	Positive	Negative	Positive	.003
Total Assets	Positive	Negative	Positive	.025
Income variable	Negative	No relationship is specified	Positive	.069
Liquidity	Positive	Negative	Positive	.076
Employee Size	Positive	Negative	Positive	3.439

Source: Computed.

The actual results of the Long term Debt ' β ' coefficients of the present study, along with the expected ones under Trade-off and Pecking order Theories are summarized in the Table 16. ICR, Tangibility, NDT, Total Assets, Liquidity and Employees Size are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Trade-off Theory. Sale Size and Growth exhibit the same signs as expected under Pecking order Theory. Income variability and Tangibility are not expected to have any specific relation under the two theories. On the whole, the result of the present study indicates an equal chance for both the theories applicable for Steel Authority of India Limited.

Table: 17 Relationship between Explanatory Variables and Leverage (TSL) with Trade-off and Pecking order Theories.

Variables	Expected Relationship		Actual Relationship and β Coefficients	
	Trade-off Theory	Pecking Order Theory	Actual Relationship	Long term Debt
Sale Size	Positive	Negative	Positive	.036
Growth	Negative	Positive	Negative	-.061
Profitability	Positive	Negative	Positive	.639
ICR	Negative	Positive	Negative	-.213
Tangibility	Positive	No relationship is specified	Negative	-.036
NDT	Positive	Negative	Positive	.730
Total Assets	Positive	Negative	Positive	.018
Income variable	Negative	No relationship is specified	Positive	.007
Liquidity	Positive	Negative	Positive	.653
Employee Size	Positive	Negative	Positive	.774

Source: Computed.

The actual results of the Long term Debt ' β ' coefficients of the present study, along with the expected ones under Trade-off and Pecking order theories are summarized in the Table 17. Probability, growth, sales size, ICR, NDT, Employee Size and liquidity are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Trade-off Theory. No variable exhibit the same signs as expected under Pecking order Theory. Income variability, tangibility and NDT are not expected to have any specific relation under the two theories. On the whole, the result of the present study indicates Trade-off Theory is only applicable to Tata Steel Limited.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study contribute towards a better understanding of financing behavior in two steel companies. Hypotheses, based on comparing the relationships between total and long term debt leverage with and eight explanatory variables represent that profitability, growth, tangibility, interest coverage ratio, assets size, liquidity, non debt tax shield and sales size, were developed to test which capital structure theories best to explain these two companies' capital structure. The results suggest that both the static trade-off theory and the pecking order theory are pertinent theories whereas there was little evidence to support the information asymmetry theory.

- It is observed that profitability, NDT, income variability, liquidity and employee size are the determinants have positive and remain determinants showed negative relationship with long-term debt variable of SAIL. On the other hand, TSL, growth, NDT and total assets showed positive and remain determinants showed negative relationship with total debt leverages.
- Tangibility, income variability, non-tax debt, liquidity and employee size have significant and other variables are insignificant statistically at 5% level of SAIL. On other hand TSL, sales size, total assets and income variability are significant and other variables insignificant at 5 % level.
- ICR, Tangibility, NDT, Total Assets, Liquidity and Employees Size are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Trade-off Theory. Sale Size and Growth exhibit the same signs as expected under Pecking order Theory. Income variability and Tangibility are not expected to have any specific relation under the two theories. On the whole, it is observed an equal chance for both the theories applicable for Steel Authority of India Limited.
- Probability, growth, sales size, ICR, NDT, Employee Size and liquidity are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Trade-off Theory. No variable exhibit the same signs as expected under Pecking order Theory. Income variability, tangibility and NDT are not expected to have any specific relation under the two theories. On the whole, it is observed Trade-off Theory is only applicable to Tata Steel Limited.

- It is found that both the companies have followed same trend with employee size.
- Tangibility and Liquidity point of view SAIL has better than the TSL
- Growth, Profitability, Income variability, Total Assets and Non tax Debt are the determinants are more influenced on Capital Structure of TSL than the SAIL.

Further, the findings of this study have delivered some insights on the capital structure of these two firms. The issue of capital structure is an important strategic financing decision that firms have to make by applying these two trade-off and pecking order theories. It is therefore important for policy to be directed at improving the information environment, managerial strategy, psychology, human capital and network ties impact on the capital structure. This may, if not monitored by concerned authority properly and timely, invite the crisis in financial sector in future.

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